

SOME INFORMATION ABOUT THE ACTIVITIES OF QUEEN GAKHVARSHODBEGIM FROM THE WORK "MATLAI SA'DAYN VA MAJMAI BAKHRAIN"

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Abstract. *The article studies the information about the life and activities of Queen Gavharshadbegim in her work "Matlai sa'dayn va majmai bakhrayn" from a scientific and critical perspective.*

Keywords: *Amir Temur, Abdurazaq Samarkandi, Shakhrukh Mirza, Gavkharshodbegim, Khurasan, Mirza Ulugbek.*

Relevance of the topic. One of the urgent issues is to study the past of our people, whose historical roots go back thousands of years and have created a unique material and spiritual culture, to enrich the growing generation with this knowledge of history, to raise in their minds a great respect for historical memory, a spirit of pride.

During the reign of Amir Temur and the Timurids, women made a significant contribution to the management of state affairs, the advancement of science, art, and culture, and there is a lot of information about their wisdom and ingenuity, courage, and nobility. One of such unique historical sources is Abdurazzoq Samarkandi's work "Matlai sa'dayn va majmai bakhrayn", in which the scientific and critical analysis and study of information about the place and role of the Timurid princess Gavkharshodbegim in the socio-political and cultural life is of significant theoretical and educational importance.

2. The level of study of the topic. The studies of our scientists on the topic: Azamat Ziyov (4), T. Fayziyev (5), P. Ravshanov (6) are noteworthy.

3. Research methods. The article uses the methods of comparative-historical, theoretical-conceptual historicism and logic, document study, comparison, and creativity.

4. Research results. The role of Gavkharshodbegim in the statehood activities of Shakhrukh Mirzo, the development of diplomatic relations, and the creative activities of Abdurazzoq Samarqandiy's work "Matlai Sadayn and Majmai Bakhrayn".

The Timurid era is one of the most important periods in the history of our homeland. Amir Temur laid the foundation for a centralized state and accomplished great things for the prosperity of the country. During this period, science, education, and culture developed greatly. Amir Temur and the Timurids supported and patronized scientists, poets, historians, and religious figures during their reign. During the Timurid period, the rulers who created in such fields as science, poetry, and literature among the representatives of the dynasty contributed to the development of science, art, and culture. We can show the Mirzo Ulugbek Academy in Samarkand and the Herat School, which reached the peak of its development during the reign of Sultan Hussein Baykara. Many valuable historical works were created during the Timurid period.

One of the most important sources for the Timurid period is Abdurazzoq Samarqandiy's "Matlai sa'dayn va majmai bakhrayn" (The Rising of Two Blessed Stars and the Confluence of

Two Seas), which covers the cultural life of that period and the creative activities of the Timurid rulers and queens.

Kamoliddin Abdurazzaq ibn Jalouddin Ishaq Samarkandi (1413-1482) was born into a family belonging to one of the wealthy and influential families of Herat. According to Abdurazzaq Samarkandi himself and the 15th-century historian Mirkhand, his father Jalaludin Ishaq Samarkandi was a "servant" at the court of Shakhrukh and worked as an imam and judge in his army (lashkari) for many years. Abdurazzaq studied well and mastered the sciences of jurisprudence, hadith, Arabic language and history. He became one of the most prominent scholars of his time. The work "Matlai sa'dayn va majmai bakhrayn" written by Abdurazzaq Samarkandi and which has come down to us was written between 1467-1470. The work consists of two volumes.

The author explains the reasons for writing the work as follows: "Now, these pages are in need of a guide, a collector, and may their repentance be accepted". Abdurazzaq ibn Ishaq as-Samarkandi says: With the support of the mighty king (god), the editor's pen, having found relief from writing the first half of the book "Matlai sa'dayn wa majmai bakhrayn" - "The rising of two blissful stars and the confluence of two seas", now the rays of the sun of thought shine from the east of the grace of the most knowledgeable king, illuminating the second half of the book towards the horizon of completion. (In this half of the book) it is hoped that the success of entering into the (narration of) the events related to the state of the glorious descendants of the great ruler (Amir Timur) in the hereafter will be achieved by the pure grace of the Almighty God, and similarly, the interpretation of the events of other cities and villages and the description of their wonders and the news of the famous kings and the monuments of powerful rulers will be sought by the blessing of the Almighty God's knowledge. He is indeed the most generous of those who are hoped for. Misra: May (God's) help be with you on this path." [1.40-b.]

After the death of Amir Timur, Shakhrukh Mirza initially strengthened his position in Khorasan, which was given to him by his father. Later, he included the territories of Movarounnahr, Khorezm, Kabul, Ghazna, Kandahar, Northern Khorasan, Persia, and Western Iran in his possessions and united them into his single state. Also, several countries such as Azerbaijan, Shirvan, and India were among the possessions dependent on Shakhrukh Mirza. It can be said that Gavkharshadbegim's activity as the first and most influential wife of the great ruler began precisely from this period. At this time, she managed Shakhrukh Mirza's harem and resolved issues related to women in the palace. Family events and weddings held in the palace were also held under the leadership of Gavkharshadbegim.

In Abdurazzoq Samarkandi's work "Matla'i savdayin va majmai - bakhrayin", the author mentions in 41 places of the book that he personally saw and knew the princess Gavkharshodbegim. The author uses various descriptions and artistic metaphors when describing her. In one place, he says "agoyi", and in another, he calls her "mahdi ulyo" (a title given to the eldest wife of the king). In the description of some events, he even calls the queen by the name of Bilqis, the queen of Saba', the wife of the prophet Suleiman. These descriptions are in harmony with her appearance, and her participation in royal banquets and dresses appropriate to these banquets are embodied before our eyes. Speaking about Gavkharshodbegim's activities at the palace, the author states that the queen also actively participated in various receptions and ceremonial receptions. "The support of the state and religion, Mirzo Ulugbek, set out from Maveronnahr towards Khurasan, and after passing through Jaihun, the news of his arrival reached

Hazrat Khagani Said. Mahdi Ulyo Gavharshod Agha, Ghiyasuddin Mirzo Baysungur, Mirzo Muhammad Jahongir, Mirzo Muhammad Jogi and other princes, nobles and great emirs met him for several farsangs, welcomed him and fulfilled the conditions of honor and respect. On the nineteenth of Rabi' al-Awwal (May 6, 1417), the prince was blessed with the honor of entering the court of Hazrat Khagani Said and was delighted to see his son, the prince - a verse -. For several days they held royal weddings and royal feasts". [1.324-p.]

From this passage it is clear that among the royal court that came out to meet the prince, there was only one princess, Gavkharshodbegim. The rest of the princesses did not participate in this solemn welcoming ceremony. This also indicates that Gavkharshodbegim had a very high position among the princesses. In addition, the fact that the name of Princess Gavkharshodbegim is mentioned in historical sources before the great emirs, nobles and princes, and her authority and influence in official circles clearly indicate that she was higher than other princesses, princes, emirs and nobles. This information is also given in Fasikh Khavofiy's work "Mujmali Fasihiy". According to it, Shakhbekach (i.e. Gavkharshodbegim) and princes were brought out to meet Mirzo Ulugbek.

When Mirza Shakhrukh left the capital for a long time due to a campaign, he left Gavkharshodbegim here to help the central government. Because the stay of this enterprising, resourceful woman in the capital was important for the peace and security of the country. Usually, Amir Temur left a prince in charge of the capital. Among the princes who were honored with such an honor, one can list Mirza Jakhongir, Mirza Umarshaikh, Mirza Mukhammad Sultan, Mirza Shakhrukh, Mirza Pirmukhammad, Mirza Umar. Although Mirza Shakhrukh left Mirza Muhammad Jogi in the capital, the historian notes that he was left for the service of Gavkharshodbegim. From this it can be seen that the management of the capital and the central government was left to Gavkharshodbegim, who was described as Mahdi Ulya, that is, "the cradle of the world". "When Hazrat Khagani Said was marching towards Iraq and Azerbaijan, Mahdi Ulya Gavharshod Agha remained in Herat as a prince and was in the service of the prince Muhammad Jogi Bahadir. When Iraq and Azerbaijan were conquered and the Turkmen emir Qara Yusuf was defeated and this news reached Khorasan and Transoxiana, Mirza Ulugbek, acting on the order of (Hadith), wanted to spend a few days (425) in the service of his famous prince, Bilqis, who was his mother. But since the prince himself found it difficult to come from Transoxiana (to Herat), he requested that Mahdi Ulya come to Samarkand. At the beginning of Rabi' al-Awwal (March 16, 1420), the throne of the holy city set out; Mirza Mukhammad Jogi was in his service. When Mirza Ulugbek heard that he had set out, he turned to his prospects and, having had the pleasure of meeting near Bukhara, they had the honor of kissing each other's feet, and together they set off in a state of peace for Samarkand, arriving in paradise-like Samarkand in the middle of Rabi' al-Akhir (April 28-29, 1420). In the middle of the month, a royal wedding and a sumptuous feast were arranged in Bogi Chinor, and after several days of joy and celebration, Mirza Ulugbek presented a gift of mules and camels, laden with sakylots, crimson carpets and other exquisite ornaments, and horses with golden saddles. Then the Mahdi Ulya set off for Khorasan, and Mirzo Ulugbek, having accompanied her with respect and honor to Rabati Yam, returned at the behest of his mother, and having said goodbye to Mirzo Mukhammad Jogi, he also showed him kindness and blessings and sent him away with his mother". [1.381-382 p.]

One of the aspects that requires attention in this information is that Gavkharshod Begim found it necessary to travel to Maveronnahr only after Mirzo Shahrukh's campaign ended in

victory. This trip was made at the request of Mirzo Ulugbek. Mirzo Ulugbek could not leave his territories in Maveronnahr and go to Khorasan due to the security of the territory. It was necessary for Mirzo Ulugbek to go and get news from his mother, who was left in the rule of Herat, and to congratulate her on this task, and to cheer her up. That is why he paid serious attention to this issue and tried to persuade his mother to travel to Maverounnahr and win her heart. In addition, there may be other political reasons for this.

The name of Gavkharshodbegim is also mentioned in historical sources because of various ceremonies that took place in the life of the palace. Ceremonies related to the birth of princes were also held in the palace as solemn events. The implementation and organization of these events was mainly the responsibility of Gavkharshodbegim. One of such events took place in 1427. This event was associated with the birth of a son by Mirza Shahrukh, one of the children of Mirza Muhammad Joqi. The newborn was named Abu Bakr. The names of only three people who participated in the event are given. These are: Mirza Shahrukh, Gavkharshodbegim and Mirza Baysunkur. This also allows us to determine the place of Gavharshadbegim in the life of the palace. This ceremony is described by Abdurazzaq Samarkandi as follows: "On the twenty-eighth of Muharram (October 18, 1427), the world was honored with the birth of the prince Abu Bakr, and the body of the baby born with this blessed outcome gave the world a wealth of brilliance and beauty. Mahdi uly Gavharshod aga, Mirzo Baysungur and Arkoni performed the state congratulatory ceremonies and brought sokhki and nisars. His Excellency, having seen the wedding preparations, signaled to organize a party. A gathering like a paradise (party) was organized, which would make the Chinese court jealous". [1.496-b]

The work "Matlai sadayn va majmai bahrayn" by the famous historian of the 15th century Abdurazzaq Samarkandi is one of the most important sources on the history of the Timurids. This work stands out from other centuries with the rarity and reliability of the events it contains and serves as a valuable source in our study of history.

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